

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№2

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 1051 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 7-fevralda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

“Yashil universitet” tamoyillari: mazmun-mohiyati va ahamiyati	20
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
“Yashil universitet” tamoyili asosida barqaror rivojlanish rejasi va institutsional chora-tadbirlar amaliyoti	26
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich	
O‘zbekistonda davlat mulkini xususiylashtirishning yangi bosqichiga o‘tmoqda	31
Shadmanov Erkin Sherkulovich	
The Impact of Technological Advancements on SME Growth: Trends and Case Studies in Uzbekistan	35
Tojiyev Abror, Raxmonaliyev Abbas	
Оценки эффективности деятельности малого бизнеса	45
Ортиков Улугбек Акробек угли	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda cheklangan resurslarning cheksiz imkoniyatlari	51
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyotining barqaror rivojlanishida tijroat banklarining o‘rni	57
Xakimova Feruza Nazarovna	
Biznesning ijtimoiy ma‘suliyati konsepsiyasining rivojlanish bosqichlari	62
M.O. Kasimova	
Korporativ boshqaruvda risklarni boshqarish va risk darajasini pasaytirish yo‘llari	68
Mallayev Salohiddin Saidkamolovich	
Взаимосвязь стратегии управления персоналом и бизнес стратегии организации	74
Давлетов Ислom Халикович, Бикмаев Тимур Рафаелевич	
Iqtisodiyotning barqaror va izchil rivojlanishida ishlab chiqarishni mahalliyashtirishning o‘rni	78
Sobitova Ra‘no Solidjonovna	
Statistik kuzatuvlarni samarali tashkil qilishda raqamli texnologiyalardan keng foydalanishdagi mavjud muammolar	82
Istoraxon Abdusalomova Ilhom qizi	
Xizmat ko‘rsatish korxonalarida risklarni diversifikatsiya tahlili	87
Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o‘g‘li	
Korxonalarda raqamli marketing: nazariy asoslar va amaliy imkoniyatlar	94
Amonov Mirzohid Tuymuratovich	
Enhancing post-quantum security through hybrid cryptographic systems integrating quantum key distribution	98
Shuxrat Toirov Abduganiyevich, Saidakhmedov Eldor Islomovich, Akbarov X.U	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda elektron tijorat bozorining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati bo‘yicha adabiyotlar tahlili	110
Sodiqov Abdulhafiz	
Mulkiy soliqlar ma‘muriyatchiligi va ulardan soliq xavfsizligini ta‘minlashda foydalanish	118
Aliyarov Olim Abdug‘aparovich	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromadlarini shakllantirishda mahalliy soliqlar va yig‘imlarning o‘rni va ahamiyati	125
Bauyetdinov M.J., Eshbanbetov E.M.	
Yuk avtomobillari transport xizmatlarining samaradorligini aniqlash ko‘rsatkichlari	130
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzoqovich, Ishonkulova Feruza Asatovna	
Arima modellari yordamida jismoniy shaxslarning xorijiy pul o‘tkazmalari ko‘satkichini prognozlashtirish (surxondaryo viloyatida)	135
Davranov Odil Jumanazarovich	
Kambag‘allikni baholash: AQSH misolida FPL	146
Durdona Davletova	
Ta‘lim xizmatlari sifatini oshirishning nazariy-ilmiy asoslari	151
Axmedova Barno Abdiyevna	

Tijorat banklarining depozit jalb qilishdagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	155
Farhod Rustamovich Bobobekov	
Трансформация потребительской этики и поведения в условиях перехода узбекистана к зеленой экономике.....	161
Хусайнов Равшан Рахимович, Кариева Латофат Саидакромовна	
Qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining samarali innovatsion rivojlanishini ta'minlash yo'nalishlari	168
Fayzullayev Jonibek Mambetsaliy o'g'li	
Comparative analysis between the fundamental and technical analysis of stocks	175
To'qmirzayev Kamol Mo'min ugli	
Тенденции устойчивого развития автотранспортных предприятий в формировании цифровой экономики.....	182
Юсупходжаева Г.Б	
Влияние маркетинга на качество продукции – стратегии успешных брендов и использование отзывов клиентов	187
Маматкулова Шоира Джалоловна	
Ma'suliyati cheklangan jamiyatlarning fond bozoriga kirish imkoniyatlari: statistika, tahlil va prognozlar	192
Butayev Javlonbek Inatillo o'g'li	
O'zbekistoning eksport salohiyatini mustahkamlash zamonaviy tendensiyalari	197
Bozorov Akmal Amonovich	
Mintaqa salohiyatini oshirishda innovatsiyalar va investitsiyalarni rag'batlantirishda klaster yondashuvining o'rni.....	203
Muxammadiyeva Yulduz Yusupovna	
Инновационная деятельность металлургических предприятий в изменяющейся среде	207
Каримов Маъруф Ихтиёрович	
Значение лизинговых услуг в финансировании основного капитала предприятий	212
Латипова Шахноза Махмудовна	
Iqtisodiyotning jadal rivojlanishini innovatsion faoliyat asosida shakllantirish yo'llari	217
Nosir Maxmudov	
Davlat xaridlarida moliyaviy nazoratni amalga oshirish muammolari	224
Abdug'aniyev Bekjon Habibulla o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish	229
Baxriyev Muxiddin Sheraliyevich	
Main directions of increasing the investment attractiveness of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan	240
Kengesov Diyorbek Umidovich, Nurniyazova Dilnoza Arzubay qizi, Xalmuratova Dilnaz Suleyman qizi, Bekjanova Gozzal Janabaevna	
Исследование оказания торгового обслуживания сельского населения.....	245
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна, Усманова Дильфуза Ильхомовна	
Развитие логистики спортивных мероприятий на основе международной практики	252
Исмагулова Гульмира Нуралиевна	
Tijorat banklari depozit xizmatlari amaliyotini takomillashtirish	257
Melikov Otabek Maxmadaminovich	
Tijorat ko'chmas mulki qiymatini baholash xususiyatlari va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	263
Xomitov K.Z.	
Improvement of accounting of authorized capital at joint-stock companies	269
Ortikov Ergashjon Yakubboevich, Xusinov Ibragim Ismailovich	
Raqamli valyutaning xalqaro savdodagi roli: imkoniyatlar va muammolar.....	274
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, To'qmirzayev Kamol Mo'min o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyot: nazariy jihatlari va ahamiyati	279
Maksumova Dildora Alisherovna	
O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlanish asoslari.....	283
Maxmudova Feruzabonu Odiljon qizi, Lutfiy Farangiz Sharidin qizi	
Oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari	288
Tursunova Dilnavoz davron qizi	

Национальная оценка рисков отмывание преступных доходов	294
Хомидов Шухрат Гафуржонович	
Inflyatsion targetlash rejimiga asoslangan monetar siyosatning makroiqtisodiy ahamiyati	301
Duskobilov Umidjon Sharofiddinovich	
Tijorat banklarining kredit mablag'laridan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	308
Ulugbek Nizamov	
Soliq bazasini aniqlash metodologiyasining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va tamoyillari	312
Xalikchayeva Sadokat Ilxomjonovna	
"Qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish va ularning iqtisodiy samaradorligi"	316
Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	
Повышение популярности банковских услуг посредством цифровых инноваций: стратегии интеграции технологий с ориентацией на клиента	318
Рузиева Олима Шухратовна, Рузиев Шухрат Нармурадович	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakatini samarali ta'minlashda xorijiy tajribalar	322
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Pul-kredit siyosatida "big data" texnologiyalari: o'zbekistonda to'lov ma'lumotlari, qidiruv so'rovlari va matn tahlilidan foydalanish istiqbollari	327
Mamatxo'jayev Otabek Farxodjon o'g'li	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash	332
Abdusamatov Mamaysup Qulmonovich, Jovliyev Ramazon Fazriddin o'g'li	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarini soliqqa tortishda chet el tajribasi	343
A.I. Akbarov	
Mamlakatda kichik biznes subyektlari va eksport sohasida samarali rivojlanish yo'nalishlari	347
M.A.Ibrohimov	
Neighborhood system of activity economic the basics improvement	351
Alikulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari evolyutsiyasi va kapitallashuv darajasini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari	356
Mamadjonov Shukurillo Ibrohimjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tijorat banklarning andarrayting jarayonlarini takomillashtirishni innovatsion usullari	360
Bobojonov Xursand Qadamovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida pensiya jamg'armasi faoliyatini takomillashtirish	374
Inoyatova Maqsuda Palvonnazirovna	
"Yashil iqtisodiyot" iqtisodiyotning barqaror rivojlanish asosi sifatida	379
Jiemuratov Temirbay Polatbaevich, Muratbaev Bayram Bazarbay uli	
Aholining daromadlarini soliqqa tortish asosida tengsizlikni kamaytirish yo'llari	384
Vosiqov Ulug'bek Alisherovich	
Soliq to'lovchilarga ko'rsatiladigan raqamli xizmatlarni ko'paytirish orqali soliq bazasini kengaytirish	389
Usmonov Ulug'bek Jaxongir o'g'li	
Совершенствование механизмов стимулирования инновационного развития промышленности: международный опыт и перспективы для узбекистана	394
Ўролова Севара Бехзод кизи	
Стратегия перехода к зеленой экономике Республики Узбекистан	399
Маматова Фатима Абдусаломовна	
Ensuring financial stability of companies international practice experience	405
Abdullayeva Madinabonu Khasanboyevna	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda investitsiya samaradorligini oshirish: barqaror o'sish strategiyasi va imkoniyatlari	409
F.U.Umarov	
Mamlakatimizda sug'urta xizmatlarining roli va ahamiyati	414
Ko'charov Murod Baxtiyorovich	
Проблемы и перспективы развития частного образования	419
Мухаммедов Мурод Мухаммедович, Мардонов Баҳодир Бахронович	
Mahalla tizimida sohaviy islohatlarni amalga oshirish zarurati	425
Karjavova Xurshida Abdumalikovna	

Iqtisodiyotni barqarorligini ta'minlashda jismoniy shaxslar daromadlarini soliqqa tortish tartibini takomillashtirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari	429
Bobomurotova Manzura Panji qizi	
Bank chakana xizmatlari amaliyotini rivojlantirishda xorij tajribasi.....	434
Saipnazarova Mohinur Utkir qizi	
Oziq-ovqat sanoati rivojlanishining xorij tajribalari va ulardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	437
Ergashev R.X., Xo'jamov J. T.	
Mintaqada sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlar bozori mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	442
Davron Kesimov	
Keytering xizmatlari turlari va uning inson omili bilan bog'likligi sifatida.....	446
Nasiba Ergasheva	
Meva-sabzavotchilik mahsulotlari kooperasiyasini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	451
Ergashev R.X.	
O'zbekistonda xizmatlar sektorini rivojlantirish va kambag'allikni qisqartirish: empirik tahlil (2000-2024)	456
S. Alikulov, M.Alikulova	
Avtotransport vositalaridan foydalanishning xorij tajribasi.....	476
Norqobilov Jaxongir	
Efficient use of resources in the production process using the example of cotton and textile clusters.....	485
Khalikov Talibjon Luptullaevich	
REPO bitimi va uning turlari hamda uning moliya bozorida barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi ahamiyati.....	490
Ibrohimov Yorqinjon To'lqin o'g'li	
Digital development of dividend policy in corporate structures in the republic of uzbekistan	498
Shermukhamedov Akmal Komiljonovich	
Tijorat banklari passivlarini tahlil qilishning metodik obzori	503
Ziyodullayev Sodiqjon Mamadillaevich	
Tadbirkorlikda ishlab chiqarish resurslari va ulardan foydalanishning ilmiy-nazariy masalalari.....	513
A.O'tbosarov	
To'g'ri soliqlarni hisoblanishi va undirilish amaliyotini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	519
Xo'jaqulov Ramshid Yunusovich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan korporativ mijozlarga ko'rsatiladigan innovatsion bank xizmatlarini shakllantirish yo'llari	526
To'laev Safarmurod Boymuhammad o'g'li	
Макроэкономический анализ механизмов стимулирования роста уровня занятости и меры для уменьшения уровня бедности в Узбекистане.....	532
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
Kapital bozorida emitentlarning investitsion jozibadorligini oshirishda dividend siyosati.....	548
Sardor Omonov	
Korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar amaliyotini rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	554
Shohyora Otaxonova	
Aylanma kapital rentabelligini baholashga kompleks yondashuv	559
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Kambag'allik muammosi tadqiq etilishining nazariy asoslari	567
Mirzaxalikov Bobir Baxtiyorovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida raqamli marketingni talabalar va oilalar qarorlarini hisobga olgan holda optimallashtirish.....	571
Xidoyatov Murod Batirovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi sohasida kooperatsiyalar rolini mustahkamlash	578
Abdufarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
O'zbekistonda oziq-ovqat sanoati korxonalarida ishlab chiqarish holati tahlili	584
Shukurov Rustam Ergash o'g'li	
Infratuzilma loyihalarini innovatsion moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirish.....	593
Yarbazarov Shavkat Butayevich	

Ko'chmas mulkni kadastr baholash xususiyatlari.....	600
To'lakov Ulug'bek Toshmamatovich	
Tijorat banklarining investitsion faoliyatini rivojlantirish	610
Dodiyev Fozil O'tkurovich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari mahsulotlarini bozor talabiga mosligini ta'minlash va raqobatni oshirish.....	614
Suyunov Jaloliddin O'ktam o'g'li	
Description of methods for assessing the competitiveness of an enterprise	620
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Sanoat korxonalarini bozor sharoitlariga moslashtirishga nazariy yondashuvlar	624
Begmullayev Otabek Irisaliyevich	
Iqtisodiy inqiroz sharoitida tadbirkorlik subyektlarida iqtisodiy inqirozga qarshi kurashish strategiyalari	630
Jo'rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
O'zbekistondagi nodavlat oliy ta'lim tashkilotlarida moliyaviy rejalashtirish metodologiyasi.....	638
Xurramov Jonibek Rustamovich	
Methodology for placing types of green bonds.....	642
Rakhmedova Madinakhon Nusrat qizi	
Tarmoqlar sohasini rivojlantirish va raqobat	647
Fayziyeva Dilafroz Shuxratovna	
Evolution of the pensions in great britain.....	650
Umarova Zulaykho Tursunovna, Rakhmanova Zilola Alisherovna	
Favqulodda ekologik vaziyatlarni bartaraf etishga doir davlat siyosatining uslubiy va tashkiliy-institutsional muammolari.....	654
Azizov T.A.	
Oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	658
Yo'ldoshev Jaxongir To'raboyevich	
Mehnat motivatsiyasi nazariyasini rivojlantirishda insoniy munosabatlar maktabining o'rni	662
Aslanov Aziz Mexmonovich	
Перспективы внедрения альтернативной системы отопления тепловыми насосами на социальных объектах узбекистана	668
Руденко Инна Юрьевна, Волков Алексей Владимирович	
Qurilish tashkilotlarida xarajatlar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	675
Abdusalomova Nodira Bakhodirovna, Qurbanov Amirulla Muradilloevich	
Turizm sanoatida ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning roli va ahamiyati.....	682
Kasimova Zilola G'ulomiddinovna	
Совершенствование эффективного управления основными активами предприятий в условиях инновационного развития	686
Мусаева Жамила Кароматовна	
Use of mobile and internet technologies state and development of culture.....	695
Boboqulov Sanjar Baxronkulovich, Uroqov Xumoyun Jamshid ugli, Ergashev Suxrobjon Mirzoxiddin ugli	
The influence of physical activity on social education and new sports trends.....	699
Axtamov Djamshed Baxromovich	
Iqtisodiyotni ekologik boshqarishning nazariy asoslari.....	705
Qodirov Abduvohid Abdumannof o'g'li	
The role of participatory budgeting practices in financing infrastructure.....	711
Mirzayev Xursanmurod Egamberdiyevich	
Основы теории факторного анализа прибыли предприятия	717
Алиева С.С.	
Yashil energetikaning mintaqaviy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	723
Raxmatullayev Umarbek Ulug'bekovich	
O'zbekistonda islomiy banklarni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	734
Nurmuxammedov Abdijabbar Yunusovich	
O'zbekistonda "yashil" iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda islomiy moliyaning ahamiyati	741
Axmedov Azamat Kamilovich, Maratova Aseliya Nurpeyis qizi	
Turistik xizmatlar bozorini rivojlantirishning nazariy-uslubiy qoidalari	746
Turayev Og'abek Kaxramonovich	

Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida kengashlar faoliyatini baholash uslubiyotini takomillashtirish.....	750
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish borasida muvaffaqiyatli tadqiqotlar.....	760
Nurmetova Muyassar Jumanazarovna	
Составление многокритериальной базы оценки эффективности и результативности предпринимательской деятельности спортивной организации.....	766
Маткаримова Наргиз Тухтасиновна	
Tijorat banklarning resurs bazasini mustahkamlash bilan bog'liq muammolari va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari.....	772
Sultanmuratova Dilrabo Shaylavbekovna	
Agroservis xizmatlari ko'rsatish qishloq xo'jaligida yaratilgan mahsulotlarning iste'mol qiymatini oshiruvchi omil sifatida.....	777
Iroda Turdibayevna Kudratova	
Shaxsda individual imkoniyatlar rivojlanishining yoshga doir xususiyatlari.....	783
Tulyaganova Gulnoza Olimjon qizi	
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasining rivojlanish bosqichlari.....	787
Xolmurzayev Sobir Nazarovich	
Ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish asnosida o'zbekistonda aholi bandligini oshirish.....	791
Ulashova Zarnigor Botirali qizi	
Ta'limda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyasini qo'llash.....	795
Radjabov Bunyod Abduxalilovich	
Tijorat banklarini soliqqa tortish tartibining guruhlanishi.....	799
Komolov Odiljon Sayfidinovich	
Davlat moliyasida davlat budjetini samarali boshqarish masalalari.....	803
Azizjon Muxiddinov, Anvar Muminov	
Xitoy iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishi.....	808
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
Ta'lim menejeri tushunchasi hamda ularning funksional vazifalari.....	815
Abdullayev O'tkir Sadullayevich	
Rekreatsiya resurslarini o'rganish bilan bog'liq nazariy yondashuvlar.....	822
Murtazayeva Gulrux Isabek qizi	
Methods of educating spiritual and will-powered virtues in the process of athletics training.....	828
Abdilaxatov Zafar Abdigapirovich	
Роль образования в развитии человеческого капитала для креативной экономики.....	837
Хужаева Василина Сергеевна	
Xitoy iqtisodiyotining mo'jizasi.....	850
Ergashev Islomjon Ilxomjon o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim xizmatlari bozori rivojlantirishning nazariy va kontseptual yondashuv masalalari.....	857
A.A.Abdisamatov	
Soliq nazoratining zamonaviy shakllarini takomillashtirishning ayrim masalalari.....	860
Suvonov Hasan Sherboyevich	
Davlat tashkilotlarida g'aznachilik va davlat xaridlari bilan bog'liq jarayonlarning ilmiy-nazariy, tashkiliy asoslari.....	865
Mamasoliyev Abrorbek Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Inoiy faoliyatdan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirishning ayrim huquqiy jihatlari.....	869
Shamshiyev Abdulla Abdixalil o'g'li	
Sug'urta kompaniyalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning amaliy jihatlari.....	874
Umirov Abdisalom To'rayevich	
Davlat qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	880
Qurbonov Javlonbek Jurabekovich, Sodikov Abdumutolib Rustamovich	
"AFRASIAB JEANS TEXTILE" MCHJ da tijorat riski darajasini pasaytirishning 2025-2028-yillargacha bo'lgan prognoz ssenariysi.....	886
Sharipova Gulmira Toxirovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi bojxona qo'mitasida bojxona menejmentini yuritilishining mavjud holati tahlili.....	892
Mirzaxmedova Dilafruz Farxatovna, Tuxbabaev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich	

Эконометрический анализ влияния туристического потока на развитие услуг общественного питания в гостиничном секторе узбекистана	898
Алиева Мусаффо Гайрат кизи	
Yangi o'zbekistonda bilvosita soliqlar bo'yicha soliq amaliyoti: xususiyatlari va hozirgi zamon muammolari.....	908
Yo'ldoshev Shohruh Boborahim o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqarish hajmini matematik modellashtirish va prognozlash	915
Fayziyev Rabim Alikulovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tez tibbiy yordam xizmatini tahlil qilish va uni boshqarish.....	922
Gafurov Abduvoitjon Xuseynovich	
Mahalliy tizimli ahamiyatga molik banklarni aniqlash tartibi	927
Ashurov Jaloliddin Eshpulatovich	
The impact of tax policy on the development of small and medium enterprises in Uzbekistan.....	932
Urinov Iqbol Vasiqovich	
Improving the efficiency of investment activity in oil and gas enterprises	938
Raxmatova M.G., G'ofurov Sh.N.	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish vositalari.....	944
Amonov Mehridin Oromiddinovich	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va xalqaro hamkorlik: global tashabbuslar va kelishuvlar	949
Baratov Diyorbek Fazliddin o'g'li, Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna	
Iqtisodiy tahlilda qo'llaniladigan iqtisodiy – matematik usullarning mohiyati	953
Omanov Sanjar Qurbonazar o'g'li	
Soliq organlari va soliq to'lovchilar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning yangi tizimi sharoitida soliq nazorati	959
Rahimova Shahlo Rajapboyevna	
Natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirishda tibbiy sug'urta mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish metodologiyasi.....	964
Ishmanova Diana Nurmamadovna	
Mamlakat moliyaviy xavfsizligini ta'minlashda fiskal siyosatdan foydalanishning ilg'or tajribalari.....	969
Azamatov Po'lat To'lqunovich	
Qoraqalpog'iston respublikasining eksport salohiyati: mavjud holat va rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	974
Abdiramanov Ruslan Abdiramanovich	
Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasida ishsizlik darajasi dinamikasini chegara avtoregressiyalaridan foydalangan holda chiziqli bo'lmagan modellashtirish konsepsiyasi	980
Rahimboyev Muxtorbek Ikrom o'g'li	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyatini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuvlardan foydalanish.....	985
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda turistik korxonalarda tadbirkorlik faoliyatini tashkil etish va rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	989
Mirzayev Abdullajon Topilovich	
Xalqaro standartlarni joriy etishning baholash mezoni va uning tadbirkorlik subektlariga ta'siri.....	993
Oqboyev Alisher Rasuljanovich	
Foydani shakllantirish va undan foydalanish	997
Shirinov Uchqun Abduxalilovich, Umidov Davlatbek Umid o'g'li	
Mamlakat tijorat banklari aktivlarining rentabellegini ta'minlash bilan bog'lik bulgan dolzarb muammolar	1002
Sheraliyev Abbas Xolmuminovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalar moliyaviy barqarorligiga ta'sir etuvchi risklar va ularni baholash usullari.....	1006
Haqberdiyev Bekzod Uktamovich	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini boshqarishda nazorat usullaridan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	1012
Sabirbayev Nurlan Karimbay o'g'li	
Обеспечение инклюзивного роста экономики Узбекистана в условиях цифровой трансформации	1020
Жазира Буранова	

Davlatning monopoliyaga qarshi siyosatining sanoat bozorlari rivojlanishiga ta'siri.....	1024
Choriyeva Ferangiz Zohidovna	
Transchegaraviy elektron tijoratni boshqarishning zamonaviy mexanizmlarini yaratish.....	1030
Rustamova Gulmira Aliqulovna	
Ta'lim sohasini rivojlantirishning asoslari.....	1037
Poshokulova Mohigul Kaxramonovna	
Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashda donli ekinlar yetishtirishning ahamiyati va xarajatlar hisobini tashkil etishning xususiyatlari	1041
Aytimbetov Qoyshibek Orazbekovich	
Mechanism of ensuring economic security of the enterprise: methodological aspect.....	1046
Sadriddinova Nigora Khusniddinovna	

MECHANISM OF ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE ENTERPRISE: METHODOLOGICAL ASPECT

Sadriddinova Nigora Khusniddinovna

PhD, researcher at Tashkent State University of Economics

ORCID: 0000-0001-6311-0264

Abstract: In this paper has been researched the issues of economic security and functioning of the enterprise, the potential for the production of goods in demand and the provision of services based on a balanced and best use of all types of resources in an unstable and uncertain market environment.

Key words: economic security, economic security of the enterprise, national security, organizational mechanism for ensuring economic security, flexibility and adaptability of the mechanism.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada korxonaning iqtisodiy xavfsizligi va faoliyati, beqaror va noaniq bozor sharoitida barcha turdagi resurslardan muvozanatli va samarali foydalanish asosida talab qilinadigan tovarlarni ishlab chiqarish va xizmatlar ko'rsatish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy xavfsizlik, korxonaning iqtisodiy xavfsizligi, milliy xavfsizlik, iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning tashkiliy mexanizmi, mexanizmning moslashuvchanligi va moslashuvchanlik.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы экономической безопасности и функционирования предприятия, потенциальные возможности производства продукции, пользующейся спросом и оказания услуг на основе сбалансированного и наилучшего использования всех видов ресурсов в нестабильной и неопределенной рыночной среде.

Ключевые слова: экономическая безопасность, экономическая безопасность предприятия, национальная безопасность, организационный механизм обеспечения экономической безопасности, гибкость и адаптивность механизма.

INTRODUCTION

In world practice, methods and mechanisms for managing the export potential of textile clusters are widely used. World practice shows that over the past twenty years, the processes of creating cluster associations of organizations have intensified. In developed countries, more than 50% of enterprises operate in clusters, and the share of the gross domestic product produced in them exceeds 60%. World experience shows that the cluster approach to the formation of national economies, as well as regional economic systems, is an important condition for increasing production efficiency, competitiveness and welfare of the population. This confirms the importance of the chosen research topic.[6]

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The dictionary of the Russian language by Ozhegov gives the following concept: "Mechanism. 1. The internal structure of a machine, device, apparatus that sets them in motion. 2. In a figurative sense: a system, device that determines the order of some type of activity." Currently, there are many opinions on the content and possibility of using the category "mechanism" in the economy. In terms of the distribution system of management, the mechanism was understood as a set of such elements as the organizational form and management structure, methods and levers of influence that ensure the effective implementation of the goals inherent in socialist production and the most complete satisfaction of public, collective and individual interests. This definition, in our opinion, has not lost its relevance in modern conditions, since the content of

Thus, L.V. Kuzmin writes: "The economic mechanism is understood as an integrated, multi-level system of forms and methods of economic management.

Methods for assessing the impact of these ties on the overall performance of an enterprise, subsystems of incentives, planning, control, standardization, accounting and analysis of economic activity." This concept takes into account the traditional mechanism of reproduction of production factors, which are designed to ensure continuous self-sufficiency of an economic entity, but does not take into account the market mechanisms of competition, pricing and the corporate mechanism of production development. Taking into account the above, the economic mechanism should be understood as an integrated multi-level system of forms and methods of management, consisting of: a mechanism of competition and pricing that generates a process of continuous adaptation of economic entities and consumers of their products taking into account market conditions; a mechanism for reproduction of production factors, which includes subsystems of incentives, planning, control, standardization and analysis of economic activity; a corporate mechanism that ensures the accumulation of share capital and its investment in development, as well as through reinvestment of profits. Summarizing the above concepts, let us consider another category - organizational and economic mechanism, the interpretations of which, proposed by various economists, are quite contradictory. The difference in the definitions of the essence of the organizational and economic mechanism (system, aggregate, or other view) is due to the fact that the authors study objects of different types and different levels of development and complexity. The market economy is diverse and multi-structured. Many economic systems operate (interact) in it, therefore, there are also many organizational and economic mechanisms that ensure the development of these systems. An analysis of the latest research in the field of organizational and economic mechanism shows that if the authors study economic relations at the level of an economic entity as a whole, or their individual aspects at the territorial, regional, sectoral level, or on the scale of the country's economy, then the authors most often consider this category as a "system". V.O. Fedorovich, studying the essence and structure of the organizational and economic mechanism of property relations, gives the following definition: "The organizational and economic mechanism of property management is a multi-level hierarchical system of the main interconnected elements and their typical groups (subjects, objects, principles, methods and instruments, etc.), as well as the methods of their interaction, including integration and disintegration, during and under the influence of which the economic relations (interests) of the state, owners (participants and shareholders), creditors and personnel, including representatives of the top management of the corporation, and society are harmonized." If the authors consider the organizational and economic mechanism as one of the aspects of the activities of an economic entity or as a separate management function, then this category is most often defined as a "set".

For example, T.A. Shilova in her work "Organizational and economic mechanism for ensuring the competitiveness of an enterprise" writes that "the organizational and economic mechanism for ensuring the competitiveness of an enterprise should be understood as a set of methods and techniques that enable an enterprise to have a stable position in the market, attract and retain consumers while implementing the main goal of its activities."

It can be said that any mechanism is functional, since there is no function without a goal. As S. N. Bulgakov wrote, "a mechanism is only a mode of action. It can work with real or apparent aimlessness or in direct opposition to human goals, but this does not mean that its very idea contradicts expediency.

Summarizing the above interpretations, when implementing the economic mechanism, we can highlight a number of processes, including the formation of production links and relations, that is, the construction of an organizational structure, the development and selection of management methods and levers that allow for the effective implementation of production goals and the interests and needs of an individual, team, and society as a whole.

When studying the nature of the organizational mechanism and the economic mechanism of enterprise management, we cannot help but take into account their close relationship, which arises because these mechanisms are implemented within the framework of one management system, therefore, they are formed under the influence of the same factors, their creation is limited by one resource potential, and they function in the same economic conditions. In our opinion, the definition of A. M. Bukreev can be considered objective, who understands the organizational and economic mechanism as "a set of organizational forms and economic methods, interconnected at the macro and micro levels into a single, regulated by legal norms, order of any direction of a type of activity." M. I. Kruglov calls the market mechanism of competition and pricing, the traditional mechanism of reproduction of production factors (the mechanism of self-sufficiency) and the joint-stock mechanism of production development (the mechanism of self-financing) the core of the economic mechanism of enterprise management. This definition gives an idea of the components of the mechanism, but does not allow us to judge its integrity.

Often the economic mechanism is identified with the system of economic incentives and management methods aimed at ensuring highly productive labor of workers, specialists and other employees, which cannot

be called an exhaustive definition. At the same time, the economic mechanism is understood as “an integrated multi-level system of forms and methods of management.” Adhering to this point of view, V.V. Shlykov includes in the design of the economic mechanism of the enterprise “a system of internal economic relations that establishes production and economic ties between structural divisions, methods for assessing the impact of these ties on the overall results of the enterprise’s activities, subsystems of incentives, planning, control, standardization, accounting and analysis of economic activity.” A constituent element of the economic mechanism of V.V. Shlykov can be seen as “a way of interaction of economic phenomena, that is, the interrelations and relations between heterogeneous economic phenomena,” which, according to French economists, in itself represents an economic mechanism.

Based on the above points of view, we will understand the mechanism for ensuring the economic security of the enterprise as an integral system consisting of separate, relatively independent, but at the same time interconnected and interacting structural elements. The main elements of the mechanism include: the form of production organization, economic or business ties (relations), the incentive system, management, planning, financing, taxation, pricing.

The mechanism for ensuring economic security of the enterprise is designed to ensure the creation of conditions motivating the effective operation of all elements of the enterprise, a high degree of coordination of public corporate and personal needs and interests. The mechanism should contribute to ensuring economic security at the input and output of the system, create reliable conditions for the operation of the managing and managed systems. The mechanism for ensuring economic security is a scheme of actions to neutralize external and internal threats to entrepreneurial activity by coordinating the economic interests of owners, personnel and external interacting parties.

The structure of the mechanism is aimed at a practical solution to the problem of transition to a higher level of economic security of business, with various combinations of resources, the use of differentiated tools and the implementation of a system of measures for safe business development. The main principles of building the mechanism of economic security of an enterprise are: purposefulness, vertical subordination, taking into account the diversity of interests of enterprise entities at all levels of the hierarchical ladder, information security, continuity, feedback, organization and consistency, legality. Practical actions to ensure economic security are based on the regulatory framework for the activities of enterprises, economic incentive measures, methods of implementing economic security policies, administrative control levers, personnel motivation, ensuring compliance between profitability and risk, optimizing the “volume-cost-profit” ratio, logistics chains, modernization, resource conservation, and others. Administrative instruments include various regulations, standards, and permits, but in a market economy they should be used with great caution.

Therefore, in our opinion, such financial instruments as subsidies, preferential taxation, and government spending on infrastructure should be most widely used. It should be borne in mind that financial assistance used in large amounts can have an extremely strong impact on the production system. It is necessary to apply information and consulting measures more widely and actively.

In particular, in certain cases it is necessary to activate public opinion through the media, and also to strive for mutual coordination of goals and means of achieving them in the form of economic and political mechanisms. A qualitatively new type of financial intermediation, reducing the degree of risk and uncertainty, is information support for clients, primarily investors, which is based on a system of consulting and marketing services provided to investors, as well as on participation in the process of asset management or in the creation of a collective investment system.

The economic security of an enterprise is impossible without expanded reproduction of all aspects of fixed capital. This process should be reflected in a steady increase in the technical, energy and information equipment of production, equipping all sectors of the economic complex with advanced technology and, ultimately, serve as a stable basis for an intensive type of expanded reproduction.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

It should be especially emphasized that the expanded reproduction of fixed capital and its proportions have a long-term, long-term impact on all aspects of the functioning of a market enterprise, since they are the foundation of its long-term development. The main condition for the expanded reproduction of fixed capital is large capital investments carried out along with the process of improving the use of existing equipment. An important quantitative indicator that characterizes the presence of expanded reproduction of fixed capital is a large amount of capital investments compared to the amounts of depreciation charges, since depreciation charges allow only simple reproduction. In conclusion, the presentation of the mechanism for increasing the economic security of an enterprise, formed on the basis of scientific approaches and principles using basic and applied theories, in a broad and narrow sense, states the multiplicity of its elements, which proves the

complexity of the security process. In this regard, it is necessary to select specific tools of the mechanism depending on the operating conditions of the enterprise, the stage of development of its financial and economic activities, and, as a consequence, on the current level of economic security of the enterprise.

References:

1. Senchagov, V.K. Economic security [Text] /V. Senchagov.- M., 2010.
2. Senchagov, V.K. Economic security of Russia [Text] / V.K. Senchagov.- Publisher: "Delo", Moscow, 2005.- 896 p.
3. Serbinovsky, B.Yu. Theory and methods of diagnostics of production systems [Text]: diss... doctor of economic sciences: 08.00.05.- Novocherkassk, 2001.
4. Sigitova, N.N. Development of a methodology for diagnosing the economic security of an enterprise [Text] / N.N. Sigitova//Aval.-2007.-№4.-C41-
5. Loktionova Yulia Andreevna dissertation "Tools for ensuring economic security of an enterprise in the framework of implementing its development strategy".
6. Mantaeva E.I., Goldenova V.S. On the role of an industrial cluster in the development of a regional economy // Bulletin of VoISU. Series 3: Economy. Ecology. 2017. No. 1 (38). P. 46. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 2

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
